

MULTIGROUP DIFFERENCES IN MARKETING PERFORMANCE OF LOCAL TRADERS AND MIGRANTS IN THE BORDER AREA OF BENGKAYANG REGENCY, WEST KALIMANTAN

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Abstract

This study examines the differences in marketing performance between local business actors or traders and migrants in the border area of bengkayang regency. The border area is an exciting research area, and one of the attractions comes from the perspective of business actors (msmes). Marketing performance is complex and cannot be directly measured (latent variable). The analysis method used in this study was Multigroup analysis using structural equation models (SEM). The sample was 126 local traders and 111 migrant traders. The modelling of exogenous latent variables, namely market reading ability (x1), entrepreneurial orientation (x2), and competitive advantage mediation variables (y), was tested in this study against endogenous latent variables of marketing performance (z). The data is divided into groups, and a model has been created. According to the statistical tests, the overall model fit was good for both groups. Furthermore, the results showed that, in addition to the variables of entrepreneurial orientation, the factors of market understanding capacity and upper hand influence promoting execution. Exogenous idle factors, namely marketing capability (x1), entrepreneurial orientation (x2), and competitive advantage mediation variables (y), were tested in this study against endogenous latent variables of marketing performance (z). The statistical tests showed that the overall model fit was satisfactory for both groups. Furthermore, the results showed that the factors of market understanding capacity and upper hand have affected promotion, except for the variables of entrepreneurial orientation.

Keywords: Multigroup, SEM, Local and Migrant

1. INTRODUCTION

The border is known as the demarcation line that separates one country or state from another. The people of a particular area initially did not feel very different from one another because they had the same ethnic background. The emergence of the state, coupled with state requirements, led to their separation, and they developed their own rules and regulations (Zain, 2010). West Kalimantan has five regencies directly facing the border: Sambas, Bengkayang, Sanggau, Sintang, and Kapuas Hulu (Abau, 2019). Because of the increasingly open access to the border area, migrants do business, which is why Bengkayang Regency is the ideal location

for researching the region's characteristics and trade activities. According to cultural motives, culture is a collection of principles, beliefs, and behaviours that enable one to achieve goals. According to the motives, the economy emerges from the interaction of people to fulfil their daily needs (necessities) carried out by the original community to create business opportunities for the local people, who will be referred to as local traders in the future.

Marketing performance in border areas among business actors with varying behaviours, abilities, and characteristics is fascinating. The ability to read the market impacts targeted marketing performance, which should be considered in the marketing strategy field (Lagat & Frankwick, 2017). The ability to utilize the market refers to the ability of business entertainers to figure out the market in terms of cost setting, the ability to communicate market products and distribution strategies, and the ability to develop products that will bring profits to their business field (Melewar et al., 2017). The ability of business actors to satisfy customers and recognize competitors' movements so that their business can place customers and competitors in harmony can demonstrate market understanding. Because there was a competition to win the market, the behaviour and characteristics of trade in the border area of Bengkayang Regency, which was initially carried out by residents and became an opportunity for the arrival of outside traders (migrant traders), affected marketing performance among actors. As a result, this study aimed to determine whether there are differences in marketing performance between local and migrant business actors in the border area.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

To build a competitive advantage, MSME actors must use their available resources and organizational expertise effectively. In the RBV approach, users can consider a company's resources as enduring competitive advantages (Lee, C., Lee, K. and Penning, 2001). RBV can be classified as a monetary asset (Lee, C., Lee, K. furthermore, Writing, 2001). RBV can be determined using financial assets, significant assets, human relations, organization, and technology (Man, 2001). According to Day (1994), RBV can be described in two ways: resources and capacities. The asset advantage rule is established when an enterprise gains an asset advantage. The asset greatness hypothesis mentions assets as an essential component. The asset-based approach had seen the organization as a collection of investments and acquisitions. When an organization's support and capabilities differ from its competitors thus, the organization gains an advantage. The speculation of RBV is how the organization can compete with other organizations to gain an advantage in dealing with assets owned by the organization's capacities (Nuryakin, 2018).

According to (Hou, J.J. and Chien, 2010), the ability to utilize the market is perhaps the most prevalent resource and is the way to keep up with intensity. To compete successfully, a company should research the market and develop the skills and knowledge required to enter new, lighter business sectors. According to data from (Hou, J.J., and Chien, 2010), organizations must foster market retention capacities by utilizing the ability to use the information to survey new requirements and acclimate and apply them for the organization's improvement to enter new business sectors (Nuryakin & Ardyan, 2018).

Entrepreneurial orientation is primarily associated with ideas for new enterprises, which can alter the market in various ways. Sulistyono and Ayuni (2020). Entrepreneurial orientation improves the partnership's capabilities and manages the cost of technical information, a methodology that allows the introduction of technology solutions to suffer the indispensability of consumers (Gatignon, Hubert, and Xuereb, 1997). (Workman, 1993). Several studies on entrepreneurial orientation have found a link between it and other variables, such as business actor performance (Matsuno, Ken, Mentzer, John T., and Zsomer, 2002). Other countries and global competition are increasing pressure on small and medium-sized businesses.

Darius (2016) explained the importance of an entrepreneurial orientation for businesses in today's intense market competition and pressures. SMEs with excellent entrepreneurial spirit and foresight can develop business activities oriented toward market needs. The owner, with a strong entrepreneurial spirit and orientation, is someone who can bring change and increase SMEs' potential for growth (Fatikha et al., 2021). The business will inevitably fail if the company's owner can't stay resilient to challenge those difficulties (Arif, 2011).

An advantage is an upper hand that improves an industry more than its competitors. The advantage is expected to have the ability to achieve the expected benefits, increase the overall industry share, increase consumer loyalty, and proceed with the suitability of a business (Sukaatmadja et al., 2021). A business entertainer is considered to have a competitive advantage if the business entertainer succeeds in performing a necessary procedure. The guideline of competitive advancement is the ability of top management to comprehend the preserver of overseeing MSME techniques and interpret into the chief expertise for organizations to cause and dominate open doors (Chelliah, S., Pandian, S., Sulaiman, M., and Munusamy, 2010). (Huang, K.C., Lu, N., Chang, W.J., Chang, H.C., and Chen, 2012). This technique is also not used by other organizations, both now and in the future, where the organization benefits from this methodology (Yasa et al., 2020).

Promotion is a component used to evaluate the effectiveness of organizational procedures (Harini & Yulianeu, 2019). Promoting performance is the proportion of success from an organization, association, or general promoting process activities. Moreover, marketing performance can be viewed as a concept used to measure the extent to which a product has achieved market success (Parengki, 2012). The company's strategy consistently aims to achieve excellent marketing execution (such as volume and growth rate) and high financial commissions (Pramesti, 2012). Marketing capability affects marketing performance (Murray et al., 2011), (Lagat & Frankwick, 2017); (Liang & GAO, 2020). Moreover, (Vorhies & Morgan, 2005); (Ripollés & Blesa, 2012) assert that the ability to read the market can be directly correlated with business performance; consequently, the development of marketing expertise and skills, enabling money managers to determine client preferences and competitors' activities, is a crucial element for business success. Consequently, business entertainers are anticipated to be in a position to provide superior products/services than competitors (Ripollés & Blesa, 2012). This will increase the client's desire to make purchases and improve marketing performance.

According to Weerawardena (2003), if a collection emphasizes being proactive in its business activities, it has managed to win the pioneering practices that will consequently brighten high-promoting execution. According to research (Fatikha et al., 2021), your attitude toward entrepreneurship positively and significantly affects market performance. The ability of business actors to use market intelligence and be aware of market changes will allow them to predict consumers more precisely. In other words, the ability to read the market can enable MSMEs to collect and interpret market information to gain a competitive advantage (Tejumade V. Adeniran, 2012). Furthermore, (Yao & Qin, 2016) shows that the upper hand eliminates the link between advertising capacity and execution. All findings imply that promoting abilities influence advertising execution via the upper hand's go-between role. According to (Mustafa et al., 2015), entrepreneurial orientation has a positive and significant impact on competitive advantage. Other research (Mohamed & Hanafi, 2013) found insufficient intercession between creative direction and SME execution. Furthermore, previous research has shown that upper hands have a significant and fundamental influence on organizational implementation (Wijetunge, 2016).

As stated by (Fatikha et al., 2021) that the upper hand affects promotion, where the upper hand created by the organization can further develop business results by the company can improve business results. Saiman (2014) suggests that a competitive edge is expected to generate adequate profits for planning, growing market share, boosting customer happiness, and ensuring a business's survival. According to (Chelliah S., Pandian S., Sulaiman M., & Munusamy, 2010), competitive advantage is a value-creation strategy that increases SMEs' performance. The advantage of receiving a competitive benefit is the ability of top management to comprehend how the information base of SME leftover extended and transformed into center skills that free the organization to set out and control emerging opportunities.

Based on the framework, hypotheses can be as follows:

- H1. Marketing capability to read the market affects marketing performance
- H2. Entrepreneurial orientation affects marketing performance
- H3. Marketing capability affects competitive advantage
- H4. Entrepreneurial orientation affects competitive advantage
- H5. Competitive advantage affects marketing performance.

The Model of this study can be described in the form of a flowchart as follows:

Figure 1: Research Model

3. METHODOLOGY

The exogenous variables in this study are market reading ability (X1), entrepreneurial orientation (X2), competitive advantage mediation variables (Y), and marketing performance (Y) (Z). The population consists of border business actors, local and migrant traders. Because the number of business actors (clothing, handicraft, food, household furniture, restaurants, and other services) is unknown, the snowball sampling method is used to meet the data analysis needs. In this study, two groups were established, local traders and migrant traders, to examine the differences in performance between the two groups using a multigroup approach to these categories. The number of samples determined using the first approach is a minimum sample (between 100-200) for each group, with local traders researchers use underlying condition displaying to test their research hypothesis. This study uses primary condition displaying to test alternative mediation models for existing data. Multi-group analysis allows investigators compare model results between local and entrant traders. Structural equation model was conducted in to two steps (McDonald & Ho, 2002). In the first step, a person checks the adequacy of instrument measurements. In the second step, one tests the hypothesis (direct/indirect) relationship between constructions. Confirmatory factor analysis is conducted on market reading ability, entrepreneurial orientation, competitive advantage, and marketing performance to assess construct validity. The suggested model field was matched by analysis (Hu & Bentler, 1998).

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Goodness of Fit WarpPLS

Testing Goodness of Fit using values predictive-relevance (Q^2) shows that R^2 for each endogenous in this study are: Marketing Performance (Z) obtained R_1^2 in local swords 0.31 and competitor (Y2) obtained R_3^2 s 0.46, while for migrants swords as 0.54 and competing favors (Y2) were obtained R_3^2 s 0.13

Value of *predictive-relevance* each trader is as follows:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R_1^2) (1 - R_2^2) (1 - R_3^2)$$

The calculation results can be submitted as follows:

$$Q^2 \text{ Local trader} = 0.62$$

$$Q^2 \text{ Migrant trader} = 0.60$$

4.2. Model Fit and Quality Indices

Table 1: Analysis Results Model Fit and Quality Indices

No	Model fit and quality indices	Criterion Fit	Analysis Results			
			Local Traders		Migrants Traders	
1	Average path coefficient (APC)	P < 0,05	0,276 P<0,001	Baik	0,258 P<0,001	Baik
2	Average R-squared (ARS)	P < 0,05	0,386 P<0,001	Baik	0,335 P<0,001	Baik
3	Average adjusted R-squared (AARS)	P < 0,05	0,374 P<0,001	Baik	0,321 P<0,001	Baik
4	Average block VIF (AVIF)	Acceptable if <= 5; ideally <= 3,3	1,283	Ideal	1,685	Ideal
5	Average full collinearity VIF (AFVIF)	Acceptable if <= 5; ideally <= 3,3	1,572	Ideal	2,100	Ideal
6	Tenenhaus GoF (GoF)	Small >= 0,1; medium >= 0,25; large >= 0,36	0,505	Baik	0,487	Baik
7	Sympson's paradox ratio (SPR)	Acceptable if >= 0,7; ideally = 1	1,000	Ideal	1,000	Ideal
8	R-squared contribution ratio (RSCR)	Acceptable if >= 0,9; ideally = 1	1,000	Ideal	1,000	Ideal
9	Statistical suppression ratio (SSR)	Acceptable if >= 0,7	1,000	Ideal	1,000	Ideal
10	Nonlinear bivariate causality direction ratio (NLBCDR)	Acceptable if >= 0,7	1,000	Diterima	1,000	Diterima

Source: Data Processed 2022

4.3. Differences in Indicators of Local Traders and migrants

The real difference in indicators between local traders and migrants can be seen in the following Table:

Table 2: Calculation of Invariant Outer Model of Local Traders and Migrant Traders

Outer Model		Outer loading Group		Differences	
Indicator	Notation	Local Traders	Migrant Traders	Value	Information
Changes in customer tastes	X11	0,485	0,388	0,097	Beda
Seeing changes in competition	X12	0,461	0,395	0,066	Beda
Distribution capability	X13	0,464	0,413	0,051	Beda
Desire to Excel	X21	0,418	0,379	0,039	Beda

Dare to Take Risks	X22	0,415	0,377	0,038	Beda
Future Orientation	X23	0,431	0,375	0,056	Beda
Product Differentiation	Y1	0,360	0,430	0,007	Beda
Service quality	Y2	0,366	0,432	0,066	Beda
Consumer Taste-Based Products	Y3	0,367	0,342	0,025	Beda
Sales Growth	Z1	0,415	0,418	0,003	Beda
Advantage	Z2	0,392	0,392	0,000	Beda
Number of Subscribers	Z3	0,407	0,413	0,006	Beda

Source: Data Processed 2022

5. INNER MODEL ANALYSIS RESULTS OF WARPPLS

Direct Influence Testing

The structural Model was used to test hypotheses through a t-test (T-Statistic) on each path of direct influence. The coefficient and p-esteem after the effects of the comprehensive examination should be visible in Table 3 and Figure 4.1

Table 3: Hypothesis Testing Results in Inner Model

Relationship	Local Traders		Information	Migrant Traders		Information
	Path Coefficient	p-value		Path Coefficient	p-value	
Marketing Capability (X1) → Marketing Performance (Z) (H1)	0.200	0.010	Significant	0.575	<0.001	Significant
Orientation entrepreneurship (X2) → Marketing performance (Z) (H2)	0.005	0.476	Non-Significant	0.057	0.272	Non-Significant
Marketing capability (X1) → Competitive advantage (Y) (H3)	0.138	0.056	Significant	0.113	0.110	Significant
Orientation entrepreneurship (X2) → Competitive advantage (Y) (H4)	0.607	<0.001	Significant	0.291	<0.001	Significant
Competitive advantage (Y) → Marketing performance (Z) (H5)	0.6432	<0.001	Significant	0.256	0.002	Significant

Source: Data Processed 2022

Figure 2. Local

Figure 3: migrant

The results of the evaluation (calculation of the direct inner Model) in Table 3 show that the results for hypothesis 1 influence market reading performance on marketing performance for both local and migrant traders. While hypothesis 2 shows that the results of local traders' entrepreneurial orientation have no (non-significant) impact on advertising execution, pioneering direction influences the presentation of nearby traders through the upper hand in a roundabout way. This is the same as entrant merchants' entrepreneurial orientation toward marketing performance, which does not directly involve marketing performance. It is well known that reading the market affects the competitive advantage of both local and entrant traders. Furthermore, in hypothesis 4, entrepreneurial orientation impacts competitive advantage in both local and entrant traders. In hypothesis 5, it is well known that there is a relationship between competitive advantage and marketing performance for both local and new traders.

The results above have shown that the variants of the two groups differ. Furthermore, the significance of the path coefficients differs between groups one and two. Because the variance and importance of the two groups differ, the Smith-Satterthwaite test was used to determine whether there were any differences in the influence of each variable interaction of market reading ability, entrepreneurial orientation, and competitive advantage on the marketing performance of local traders and entrant traders. This method does not require the data to be expected, the efficiency of the two groups to be the same, or the variance of the two groups to be the same (invariance).

The path coefficient and error standard of each sample group is calculated using the formula below to obtain the t-statistical value as follows:

$$= \frac{\theta^{(1)} - \theta^{(2)}}{\sqrt{\frac{n^{(1)} - 1}{n^{(1)}} se^2_{\theta^{(1)}} + \frac{n^{(2)} - 1}{n^{(2)}} se^2_{\theta^{(2)}}}}$$

Table 4: Calculation Result (T Calculate) Differences in Interaction between Variables of Local Traders and Migrants

Relationship	T count	Information*
KMK - KP	0,976	Same
OK - KP	0,002	Same
KMK - KB	0,124	Same
OK - KB	1,467	Same
KB - KP	0,932	Same

Source: Data processed 2022

Ket : *T Table = 2,78

Table 4 shows no difference between the interaction of local and migrant traders; the underlying thing is that there is no such difference among others. The interaction process within the trader group occurs influenced by regional proximity, the similarity of fate, consumers who want to be achieved the same, the similarity of professions, similarity of thoughts, contact, and communication between traders.

5. CONCLUSION

Referring to the result and discussion, thus it can be concluded that all factors influence displaying execution for speculation testing, except for the variable of driving direction, which does not directly affect marketing execution for both neighborhood brokers and settler merchants. Based on the multigroup tests, there is no difference in performance between local and migrant traders because their areas are close, and communication between merchants and consumers is not different.

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References

- Arif, A. L. (2011). Models for Improving Marketing Performance in the Context of Environmental Adaptability. Volume 5, Pages 30–44.
- Chelliah, S., Pandian, S., Sulaiman, M., & Munusamy, J. (2010). The moderating effect of firm size: Internationalization of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in the manufacturing sector. *African Journal OfBusiness Management*, 4, 3096-3109.
- Darius. (2016). The Effect of Entrepreneurial Orientation and Quality Management on Competitive Accredited by Ministry of Research and Technology Republic of Indonesia, No 200/M/KPT/2020 ISSN: 1693-5241 457 Effect of Entrepreneurship Orientation and Market Orientation on. *Agrippa*, Volume 2, Pages 199–207.
- Fatikha, C., Rahayu, M., & Sumiati, S. (2021). Effect of Entrepreneurship Orientation and Market Orientation

- on Marketing Performance Through Competitive Advantage. *Jurnal Aplikasi Manajemen*, 19(2), 448–458. <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.jam.2021.019.02.20>
- Gatignon, Hubert and Xuereb, J.-M. (1997). Strategic orientation of the firm and new product performance. *Journal of Marketing Research* : 34: 77-90. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/002224379703400107>. [Links]
 - Harini, C., & Yulianeu. (2019). Meningkatkan Kinerja Pemasaran UMKM Kota Semarang melalui Strategi Penetrasi Pasar Universitas Pandanaran. *Ikraith-Ekonomika*, 2(1).
 - Hou, J.J. and Chien, Y. T. (2010). The effect of market knowledge management competence on business performance: a dynamic capabilities perspective", *International Journal of Electronic Business Management*, Vol. 8 No.
 - Hu, L., & Bentler, P. M. (1998). Fit Indices in Covariance Structure Modeling: Sensitivity to Underparameterized Model Misspecification. 3(4), 424–453.
 - Huang, K.C., Lu, N., Chang, W.J., Chang, H.C., & Chen, J. . (2012). Correlates of perceived competitive advantage among hospital management: A multilevel Analysis. *Journal of Experimental & Clinical Medicine*, pp. 4, 170–174.
 - Lagat, C., & Frankwick, G. L. (2017). Marketing capability, marketing strategy implementation, and performance in small firms. *J. for Global Business Advancement*, 10(3), 327. <https://doi.org/10.1504/jgba.2017.10005516>
 - Lee, C., Lee, K. and Penning, J. . (2001). "Internal capabilities, external networks, and performance: a study on technology-based ventures." *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 22 No. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1002/smj.181>.
 - Liang, X., & Gao, Y. (2020). Marketing performance measurement systems and firm performance: Are marketing capabilities the missing links? *European Journal of Marketing*, 54(4). <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-05-2018-0302>
 - Man, T. (2001). "Entrepreneurial competencies and the performance of small and medium enterprises in the Hong Kong services sector." Ph.D. Dissertation, Hong Kong Polytechnic University.
 - Matsuno, Ken, Mentzer, John T. and Özsomer, A. (2002). The effects of entrepreneurial proclivity and market orientation on business performance. *Journal of Marketing*, 66(3): 18-. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.66.3.18.18507>. [Links]
 - Mcdonald, R. P., & Ho, M. R. (2002). Principles and Practice in Reporting Structural Equation Analyses. 7(1), 64–82. <https://doi.org/10.1037//1082-989X.7.1.64>
 - Melewar, T. C., Foroudi, P., Gupta, S., Kitchen, P. J., & Ford, M. M. (2017). Integrating identity, strategy, and communications for trust, loyalty, and commitment. *European Journal of Marketing*, 51(3), 572–604. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-08-2015-0616>
 - Mohamed, R., & Hanafi, N. (2013). The Impact of Corporate Entrepreneurship on Company Growth in a Hostile Business Environment. 7th Global Conference on Business & Economics, 4(1), 82–90.
 - Murray, J. Y., Gao, G. Y., & Kotabe, M. (2011). Market orientation and performance of export ventures: The process through marketing capabilities and competitive advantages. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 39(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-010-0195-4>
 - Mustafa, H., Rehman, K. U., Ahsan, S., Zaidi, R., Iqbal, F., & Studying, ". (2015). Studying the Phenomenon of Competitive Advantage and Differentiation: Market and Entrepreneurial Orientation Perspective. *Journal of Business and Management Sciences*, 3(4), 111–117. <https://doi.org/10.12691/jbms-3-4-2>

- Nuryakin. (2018). Competitive advantage and product innovation: Key success of Batik SMEs marketing performance in Indonesia. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 17(2).
- Nuryakin, & Ardyan, E. (2018). SMEs' marketing performance: the mediating role of market entry capability. *Journal of Research in Marketing and Entrepreneurship*, 20(2), 122–146. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRME-03-2016-0005>
- Ripollés, M., & Blesa, A. (2012). International new ventures as "small multinationals": The importance of marketing capabilities. *Journal of World Business*, 47(2), 277–287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2011.04.015>
- Sukaatmadja, I. P. G., Yasa, N. N. K., Rahyuda, H., Setini, M., & Dharmanegara, I. B. A. (2021). Competitive advantage to enhance internationalization and marketing performance woodcraft industry: A perspective of resource-based view theory. *Journal of Project Management*. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.jpm.2020.9.002>
- Sulistyono, H., & Ayuni, S. (2020). Competitive advantages of SMEs: The roles of innovation capability, entrepreneurial orientation, and social capital. *Contaduria y Administracion*, 65(1). <https://doi.org/10.22201/FCA.24488410E.2020.1983>
- Tejumade V. Adeniran. (2012). Investigating the dynamic capabilities and competitive advantage of South African SMEs. *African Journal of Business Management*, 6(11), 4088–4099. <https://doi.org/10.5897/ajbm11.1673>
- Vial, P., Doula, P., & Engineering, T. (2002). *Fi na l Fi na l*. January, pp. 64–72.
- Vorhies, D. W., & Morgan, N. A. (2005). Benchmarking marketing capabilities for sustainable competitive advantage. *Journal of Marketing*, 69(1), 80–94. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.69.1.80.55505>
- Weerawardena, J. (2003). I was exploring The Role Of Learning Capabilities In Innovation-Based Themes : Strategy, Competitiveness, and Learning. *Organizational Learning and Knowledge 5th International Conference 30 May 02 June 2003*, 1–16.
- Wijetunge, W. A. D. . (2016). Service Quality, Competitive Advantage and Business Performance in Service Providing SMEs in Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 6(7), 720–728. www.ijsrp.org
- Workman, J. P. (1993). Marketing's Limited Role in New Product Development in One Computer Systems Firm, *Journal of Marketing Research*, 30: 405–42. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/002224379303000402>. [Links]
- Yao, Q., & Qin, H. (2016). Marketing capability, competitive advantage, and business performance. *International Journal of Technology, Policy, and Management*, 16(3), 195–213. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJTPM.2016.079242>
- Yasa, N. N. K., Ketut Giantari, I. G. A., Setini, M., & Rahmayanti, P. L. D. (2020). The role of competitive advantage in mediating the effect of promotional strategy on marketing performance. *Management Science Letters*, 10(12). <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2020.4.024>
- Zain, S. N. M. (2010). Perbatasan Malaysia Indonesia di Kalimantan dan Komunkasi Politik, dalam *Mengelola Perbatasan Indonesia di Dunia Tanpa Batas: Isu, Permasalahan dan Pilihan Kebijakan*. Graha Ilmu.